

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

THE STABILITY OF THE FRACTIONAL STOKES SYSTEM GENERATED BY THE ZERO-FREQUENCY VECTOR IN NONLINEAR OPTICS

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Abstract

The main purpose of this paper is to study one type of fractional-order system with Caputo derivative associated to single Stokes pulse. This type of fractional pattern is determined by the zero-frequency vector. The dynamic behavior for this fractional model is investigated, including: the asymptotic stability around its equilibrium states, the stabilization problem using appropriate linear controls and the numerical integration based on the Adams-Moulton algorithm.

Keywords: Fractional Stokes system, asymptotic stability, control of stability, numerical integration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The theory of fractional differential equations (i.e. fractional calculus) is an interesting field of mathematics based on a generalization of integer derivatives to fractional-order [22, 25]. The study of this field is very important and attractive because several phenomena have been proven to be better described by fractional derivatives that take into account not only the local properties, but also global correlations of dynamical systems [6, 11, 28].

The fractional calculus has deep and natural connections with many fields of science and engineering [2, 12, 23]. In the last three decades, one increasing attention has been paid to the study of the dynamic behaviors (in particular, the chaotic behavior) of a series of fractional-order differential systems associated to classical differential systems. These fractional models played an important role in applied mathematics ([8, 13, 18]), mathematical physics ([10, 14, 16, 20]), theoretical and applied physics ([7, 17, 27]), study of biological systems ([1, 19, 21, 26]), chaos synchronization and secure communications ([15, 24, 29]) and so on.

The class of Hamilton-Poisson systems is a rich resource for obtaining chaotic or non-chaotic fractional

dynamical systems. A famous Hamilton-Poisson system is the single Stokes pulse ([3]) which comes from nonlinear optics. The aim of this paper is focused on the study of the fractional system associated with this classical dynamic system.

This paper is structured as follows. A short presentation of the single Stokes pulse from nonlinear optics (2.5) is given in Section 2. In Section 3 we define the fractional Stokes system (3.3), associated to (2.5). For the system (3.3) is investigated an interesting type of fractional Stokes systems for which the frequency vector is $b = (0,0,0)$, denoted with (3.4). The Section 4 is dedicated to analyze of asymptotic stability of equilibrium states of the fractional model (3.4). For stabilization problem of the system (3.4), we associate the fractional Stokes system with controls (4.3). In Theorems (4.1),(4.2),(4.3) and Corollary (4.1) are established sufficient conditions on parameters $d_i, i = \overline{1,3}$ to control the chaos in the fractional systems (4.6),(4.7) and (4.8). Using the Adams-Moulton algorithm, the numerical integration of the fractional system (5.1) is presented in Section 5.

II. ABOUT THE SINGLE STOKES PULSE

For details on Hamiltonian dynamics, see e.g. [3,8].

The equations of motion for the Stokes polarization parameters of a single optical beam propagating as a traveling wave in a nonlinear medium (the single Stokes pulse) from the nonlinear optics are described by using the Stokes vector u and a Hamiltonian function H .

The Stokes vector $u = (u^1, u^2, u^3)$ is defined using the Pauli spin matrices and is called *the polarization parameters of the single Stokes pulse*. The vector $u \in \mathbf{R}^3$ is assumed to be expressed in a linear polarization basis ([3]). Let be A the transition matrix from the canonical basis of \mathbf{R}^3 to the polarization basis. Since A is symmetric, then it one can always transform to a polarization basis in which A has the diagonal form $W = \text{diag}(l_1, l_2, l_3)$, where $l_i, i = \overline{1,3}$ are the eigenvalues of A .

The Hamiltonian function H is determined by the Stokes vector u , the diagonal matrix W , and the constant vectors $a = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $c = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$. Using the vectors a and c , we define the vector $b = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$, by:

$$b = a + r c, \quad r = |u|.$$

The matrix W describes the self-induced ellipse rotation. The vectors a and c describes the effects of linear and nonlinear anisotropy, respectively.

In terms of the Stokes parameters (the components of the vector u , the Hamiltonian function $H \in C^\infty(\mathbf{R}^3, \mathbf{R}), u \rightarrow H(u)$, is defined by ([3]):

$$H(u) = u \cdot \left(\mathbf{b} + \frac{1}{2} W \cdot \mathbf{u} \right). \quad (2.1)$$

where $W = \text{diag}(l_1, l_2, l_3)$, $u = (u^1, u^2, u^3)$, $\mathbf{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3)^T$ and $\mathbf{u} = u^T$.

The diagonal matrix W and the choice of the vectors a and c generates the dynamics of the Stokes vector u with the frequency b .

In the coordinate system $Ou^1u^2u^3$, the Hamiltonian function H defined by (2.1), is written as:

$$H(u) = \frac{1}{2} [l_1(u^1)^2 + l_2(u^2)^2 + l_3(u^3)^2] + b_1u^1 + b_2u^2 + b_3u^3. \quad (2.2)$$

The dynamics of a single Stokes pulse is written as Hamilton-Poisson system, see ([3]).

More precisely, the single Stokes pulse is defined on the Lie-Poisson manifold $so(3)^*$ (the dual of Lie algebra $so(3)$) with the following bracket:

$$\{f, g\}(u) = u \cdot \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \times \frac{\partial g}{\partial u} \right), \quad (\forall) f, g \in C^\infty(\mathbf{R}^3, \mathbf{R}) \quad (2.3)$$

and the Hamiltonian function $H : so(3)^* \cong \mathbf{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$ given by (2.2).

The dynamical system defined on $so(3)^*$ with Poisson bracket $\{.,.\}$ given by (2.3), enabling the equations of motion to be expressed in Hamiltonian form:

$$\dot{u} = \{u, H\} \quad (2.4)$$

where $u \in \mathbf{R}^3$, $\dot{u} = \frac{du}{dt}$, t is the time and H is the Hamiltonian function ([26]).

Performing the calculations in the equations $\dot{u}^i(t) = \{u^i(t), H\}$, $i = \overline{1,3}$ of the system (2.4), we obtain the following differential system on \mathbf{R}^3 :

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}^1(t) = (l_2 - l_3)u^2(t)u^3(t) + b_2u^3(t) - b_3u^2(t) \\ \dot{u}^2(t) = (l_3 - l_1)u^3(t)u^1(t) + b_3u^1(t) - b_1u^3(t), \\ \dot{u}^3(t) = (l_1 - l_2)u^1(t)u^2(t) + b_1u^2(t) - b_2u^1(t) \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

where the parameters $l_i, b_i \in \mathbf{R}$, $i = \overline{1,3}$ are connected with the nature of the material and the medium ([3,26]).

The system (2.5) is called the *single pulse Stokes system*. For short, the system (2.5) will be called the *Stokes system*.

III. THE FRACTIONAL STOKES SYSTEM

For basic knowledge on fractional calculus, one may refer to ([2, 5, 22, 25]).

In this section we first present some theoretical aspects related to the analysis of the stability of a system of fractional differential equations around its equilibrium states.

We consider the fractional derivative operator D_t^q with $q \in (0,1)$ to be *Caputo's derivative*. This fractional derivative operator is often used in concrete applications.

Let $f \in C^\infty(\mathbf{R})$ and $q \in \mathbf{R}, q > 0$. The q -order Caputo differential operator [5], is described by $D_t^q f(t) = I^{m-q} f^{(m)}(t)$, $q > 0$, where $f^{(m)}(t)$ represents the m -order derivative of the function f , $m \in \mathbf{N}^*$ is an integer such that $m-1 \leq q \leq m$ and I^q is the q -order Riemann-Liouville integral operator ([5]), which is expressed as follows:

$$I^q f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(q)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} f(s) ds, \quad q > 0,$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Euler gamma function. If $q = 1$, then $D_t^1 f(t) = df / dt$.

In this paper we suppose that $q \in (0, 1]$.

In the Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^n with local coordinates we consider the following system of fractional differential equations:

$$D_t^q x^i(t) = f_i(x^1(t), x^2(t), \dots, x^n(t)), \quad i = \overline{1, n}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $q \in (0, 1)$, $f \in C^\infty(\mathbf{R}^n, \mathbf{R})$, $D_t^q x^i(t)$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of order q for $i = \overline{1, n}$ and $t \in (0, \tau)$ is the time.

A point $x_e = (x_e^1, x_e^2, \dots, x_e^n) \in \mathbf{R}^n$ is said to be *equilibrium point* or *equilibrium state* of the system (3.1), if $D_t^q x^i(t) = 0$, $i = \overline{1, n}$.

The equilibrium states of the fractional dynamical system (3.1) are determined by solving the following set of equations:

$$f_i(x^1(t), x^2(t), \dots, x^n(t)) = 0, \quad i = \overline{1, n}, \quad (3.2)$$

Definition 3.1. ([25]) The equilibrium point x_e of the system (3.1) is said to be:

(i) *(locally) stable*, if for each $\varepsilon > 0$, $\exists \delta > 0$ such that

$$\|x_e\| < \delta \Rightarrow \|x(t)\| < \varepsilon, \quad (\forall) t > 0.$$

(ii) *(locally) asymptotically stable*, if it is stable and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|x(t) - x_e\| = 0$, where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm.

The Jacobian matrix associated to system (3.1) is: $J(x) = \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial x^j} \right)$, $i, j = \overline{1, n}$.

Proposition 3.1. ([23]) Let x_e be an equilibrium point of the fractional system (3.1) and $J(x_e)$ be the Jacobian matrix $J(x)$ evaluated at x_e .

(i) x_e is locally asymptotically stable, iff all eigenvalues of the matrix $J(x_e)$ satisfy:

$$|\arg(\lambda(J(x_e)))| > \frac{q\pi}{2}.$$

(ii) x_e is locally stable, iff either it is asymptotically stable, or the critical eigenvalues of $J(x_e)$ which satisfy $|\arg(\lambda(J(x_e)))| = \frac{q\pi}{2}$ have geometric multiplicity one. γ

According to Proposition 3.1, it is easy to prove the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1. ([9]) Let x_e be an equilibrium point of the fractional system (3.1) and $\lambda_i, i = \overline{1, n}$ the eigenvalues of $J(x_e)$.

If $\lambda_i < 0$ for all $i = \overline{1, n}$, then x_e is locally asymptotically stable $(\forall) q \in (0, 1)$.

The Hamilton-Poisson system (2.5) is modelled by the following fractional differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = (l_2 - l_3)u^2(t)u^3(t) + b_2u^3(t) - b_3u^2(t) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = (l_3 - l_1)u^3(t)u^1(t) + b_3u^1(t) - b_1u^3(t), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = (l_1 - l_2)u^1(t)u^2(t) + b_1u^2(t) - b_2u^1(t) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0, 1) \quad (3.3)$$

where u^i are the Stokes polarization parameters and $l_i, b_i \in \mathbf{R}$, $i = \overline{1, 3}$.

The system (3.3) is called the *fractional Stokes system associated to (2.5)*.

Proposition 3.1. ([17]) Let The initial value problem of the fractional Stokes system (3.2) has a unique solution.

As with the nonlinear dynamics generated by the Stokes system (2.5) there are six types of fractional equations (3.3) which are physically inequivalent and which correspond to different types of optical media.

In this section we will refer to the types of fractional Stokes systems for which the parameters $l_i \in \mathbf{R}$, $i = \overline{1,3}$ meet the following condition $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

In this context there are the following four types of fractional Stokes systems:

Type 1. $b = (0,0,0)$ and $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

Type 2. $b = (0, b_2, 0)$, $b_2 \neq 0$ and $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

Type 3. $b = (b_1, 0, b_3)$, $b_1 b_3 \neq 0$ and $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

Type 4. $b = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$, $b_1 b_2 b_3 \neq 0$ and $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

The *fractional Stokes system of type 1* has the following form:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = (l_2 - l_3)u^2(t)u^3(t) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = (l_3 - l_1)u^3(t)u^1(t), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = (l_1 - l_2)u^1(t)u^2(t) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0,1) \quad (3.4)$$

where $l_i \in \mathbf{R}$, $i = \overline{1,3}$ and $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$.

The system (3.3) is called the *fractional Stokes system generated by the zero-frequency vector*. It contains the three nonlinear terms of the system (3.3) (given in general form).

Remark 3.1. The fractional Stokes system of type 2 was studied in [17], including: the asymptotic stability of its equilibrium states and the stabilization problem using suitable linear controls.

Remark 3.2. If in the fractional model (3.3) we take $q = 1$, then one obtains the system for integer-order derivative which corresponds to case 4 of the dynamics (3.3). For this dynamical system, the nonlinear stability and the problem of existence of periodic solutions are studied, see ([27]).

IV. ASYMPTOTIC STABILITY OF FRACTIONAL STOKES SYSTEM (3.4)

Let us we present the study of asymptotic stability of the fractional system (3.4) around its equilibrium states. Finally,

we will discuss how to stabilize the unstable equilibrium states of the system (3.4) via Caputo fractional derivative. For this study we apply the *Matignon's test* (Proposition 3.1).

4.1. STABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE FRACTIONAL MODEL (3.4)

In this subsection we present the study of asymptotic stability for the equilibrium states of the fractional Stokes system

generated by the zero-frequency vector (3.4).

An easy computation shows that the equilibrium states of system (3.4) are given as the union of the following three families:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &:= \{e_1^m = (m, 0, 0) \in \mathbf{R}^3 \mid m \in \mathbf{R}\}, \quad E_2 := \{e_2^m = (0, m, 0) \in \mathbf{R}^3 \mid m \in \mathbf{R}^*\}, \\ E_3 &:= \{e_3^m = (0, 0, m) \in \mathbf{R}^3 \mid m \in \mathbf{R}^*\}. \end{aligned}$$

The Jacobian matrix associated to fractional system (3.4) is:

$$J(u) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & (l_2 - l_3)u^3 & (l_2 - l_3)u^2 \\ (l_3 - l_1)u^3 & 0 & (l_3 - l_1)u^1 \\ (l_1 - l_2)u^2 & (l_1 - l_2)u^1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Proposition 4.1. *The equilibrium states $e_i^m \in E_i, i = \overline{1,3}$ are unstable $(\forall) q \in (0,1)$.*

Proof. The characteristic polynomial of the matrix $J(e_1^m) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m(l_3 - l_1) \\ 0 & m(l_1 - l_2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ is

$$p_{J(e_1^m)}(\lambda) = \det(J(e_1^m) - \lambda I) = -\lambda[\lambda^2 - (l_3 - l_1)(l_1 - l_2)m^2].$$

The characteristic polynomials of matrices $J(e_2^m)$ and $J(e_3^m)$ are the following:

$$p_{J(e_2^m)}(\lambda) = \det(J(e_2^m) - \lambda I) = -\lambda[\lambda^2 - (l_2 - l_3)(l_1 - l_2)m^2] \text{ and}$$

$$p_{J(e_3^m)}(\lambda) = \det(J(e_3^m) - \lambda I) = -\lambda[\lambda^2 - (l_2 - l_3)(l_3 - l_1)m^2].$$

The equations $p_{J(e_1^m)}(\lambda) = 0$, $p_{J(e_2^m)}(\lambda) = 0$, $p_{J(e_3^m)}(\lambda) = 0$ have the root $\lambda_1 = 0$. Since $\arg(\lambda_1) = 0 < \frac{q\pi}{2}$ for all $q \in (0,1)$, by Proposition 3.1 follows that the equilibrium states $e_i^m, i = \overline{1,3}$ are unstable for all $q \in (0,1)$. \square

4.2. CONTROLLABILITY OF CHAOTIC BEHAVIORS OF THE FRACTIONAL MODEL (3.4)

In this subsection we will apply the general method for to control the stability of fractional system (3.4), (see [9]).

Let u_e be an unstable equilibrium point of the fractional Stokes system (3.4). We associate to (3.4) a new fractional system with controls and given by:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = (l_2 - l_3)u^2(t)u^3(t) + \varphi_1(t) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = (l_3 - l_1)u^3(t)u^1(t) + \varphi_2(t), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = (l_1 - l_2)u^1(t)u^2(t) + \varphi_3(t) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0,1) \quad (4.1)$$

where $\varphi_i(t), i = \overline{1,3}$ are control functions.

If one selects the control functions $\varphi_i(t), i = \overline{1,3}$ which then make the eigenvalues of Jacobian matrix of the fractional system associated to system (3.4) for the equilibrium state u_e satisfy one of the conditions from Proposition 3.1, then the trajectories of them asymptotically approaches the unstable equilibrium state u_e in the sense that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|u(t) - u_e\| = 0$, where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. In the case when u_e is unstable, then fractional model (4.1) may exhibit chaotic behavior.

In the following we will choose the control functions $\varphi_i(t), i = \overline{1,3}$ of fractional system (4.1) to control the chaotic behavior of the respective system around its equilibrium states.

If in the fractional model (4.1) we take $\varphi_i(t), i = \overline{1,3}$ given by:

$$\varphi_1(t) = d_1(u^1(t) - u_e^1), \quad \varphi_2(t) = d_2(u^2(t) - u_e^2), \quad \varphi_3(t) = d_3(u^3(t) - u_e^3), \quad d_1, d_2, d_3 \in \mathbf{R}^*. \quad (4.2)$$

With the control functions (4.2), the fractional system (4.1) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = (l_2 - l_3)u^2(t)u^3(t) + d_1(u^1(t) - u_e^1) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = (l_3 - l_1)u^3(t)u^1(t) + d_2(u^2(t) - u_e^2), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = (l_1 - l_2)u^1(t)u^2(t) + d_3(u^3(t) - u_e^3) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0,1) \quad (4.3)$$

where $l_i \in \mathbf{R}, i = \overline{1,3}$ such that $l_1 \neq l_2 \neq l_3 \neq l_1$ and $d_1, d_2, d_3 \in \mathbf{R}^*$ are control parameters.

The fractional system (4.3) is called the *controlled fractional Stokes system associated to (4.1) at u_e* .

In the follows we will use the notations:

$$\sigma_1 = l_2 - l_3, \quad \sigma_2 = l_3 - l_1, \quad \sigma_3 = l_1 - l_2. \quad (4.4)$$

With the notations (4.4), the controlled fractional Stokes system (4.3) at u_e is:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = \sigma_1 u^2(t)u^3(t) + d_1(u^1(t) - u_e^1) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = \sigma_2 u^3(t)u^1(t) + d_2(u^2(t) - u_e^2), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = \sigma_3 u^1(t)u^2(t) + d_3(u^3(t) - u_e^3) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0,1) \quad (4.5)$$

where $d_1, d_2, d_3 \in \mathbf{R}^*$ are control parameters.

The Jacobian matrix associated to fractional model (4.5) with the controls $d_1, d_2, d_3 \in \mathbf{R}^*$ is:

$$J(u, d_1, d_2, d_3) = \begin{pmatrix} d_1 & \sigma_1 u^3 & \sigma_1 u^2 \\ \sigma_2 u^3 & d_2 & \sigma_2 u^1 \\ \sigma_3 u^2 & \sigma_3 u^1 & d_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

• **Controllability of chaotic behaviors of the fractional Stokes system (3.4) around e_1^m**

Taking $d_1 = c_{11}$, $d_2 = c_{12}$, $d_3 = c_{12}$ and $u_e = e_1^m = (m, 0, 0)$ in the fractional model (4.5) we obtain the following fractional system:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = \sigma_1 u^2(t)u^3(t) + c_{11}(u^1(t) - m) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = \sigma_2 u^3(t)u^1(t) + c_{12}u^2(t), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = \sigma_3 u^1(t)u^2(t) + c_{12}u^3(t) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0, 1) \quad (4.6)$$

where $c_{11}, c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$ are control parameters.

The system (4.6) is called the *fractional Stokes system with the controls* $c_{11}, c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.

The Jacobian matrix of the fractional Stokes system (4.6) is

$$J(u, c_{11}, c_{12}) = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & \sigma_1 u^3 & \sigma_1 u^2 \\ \sigma_2 u^3 & c_{12} & \sigma_2 u^1 \\ \sigma_3 u^2 & \sigma_3 u^1 & c_{12} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Theorem 4.1. *Let be the fractional Stokes system (4.6) with the controls $c_{11}, c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.*

1. *Let $c_{11} < 0$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$.*

(i) *Let $\sigma_2 \sigma_3 < 0$ and $q \in (0, 1)$.*

(i.1) *If $c_{12} < 0$, then $e_1^m = (m, 0, 0)$ is asymptotically stable.*

(i.2) *If $c_{12} > 0$, then e_1^m is: asymptotically stable ($\forall q \in (0, q_{01})$), stable for $q = q_{01}$ and unstable*

($\forall q \in (q_{01}, 1)$), where $q_{01} = \frac{2}{\pi} \left| \arctan \frac{|m| \sqrt{-\sigma_2 \sigma_3}}{c_{12}} \right|$.

(ii) *Let $\sigma_2 \sigma_3 > 0$ and $q \in (0, 1)$.*

(ii.1) *If $c_{12} < 0$, then e_1^m is asymptotically stable for all $m \in \left(\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2 \sigma_3}}, -\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2 \sigma_3}} \right) \setminus \{0\}$ and it is unstable*

for all $m \in \left(-\infty, \frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2 \sigma_3}}\right] \cup \left[-\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2 \sigma_3}}, \infty\right)$.

(ii.2) *If $c_{12} > 0$, then e_1^m is unstable.*

2. *Let $c_{11} > 0$, $q \in (0, 1)$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$. For all $c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$, e_1^m is unstable.*

Proof. The characteristic polynomial of $J(e_1^m, c_{11}, c_{12}) = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{12} & m\sigma_2 \\ 0 & m\sigma_3 & c_{12} \end{pmatrix}$

is $p_1(\lambda) = -(\lambda - c_{11})[(\lambda - c_{12})^2 - \sigma_2 \sigma_3 m^2]$. The roots of the characteristic equation $p_1(\lambda) = 0$ are $\lambda_1 = c_{11}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm m\sqrt{|\sigma_2 \sigma_3|}$.

Case 1. *Let $c_{11} > 0$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$.*

(i) Suppose $\sigma_2\sigma_3 < 0$. Then $\lambda_1 = c_{11}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm im\sqrt{-\sigma_2\sigma_3}$.

(i.1) We suppose that $c_{11} < 0$ and $c_{12} < 0$. In this case we have $\lambda_1 < 0$ and $\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_{2,3}) < 0$. Since

$|\arg(\lambda_i)| = \pi > \frac{q\pi}{2}$, $i = \overline{1,3}$ for all $q \in (0,1)$, by Proposition 3.1(i), it implies that e_1^m is asymptotically

stable for all $m \in \mathbf{R}$.

(i.2) For $c_{11} < 0$ and $c_{12} > 0$, we have $\lambda_1 < 0$ and $\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_{2,3}) > 0$. Applying Proposition 3.1(i),

e_1^m is asymptotically stable, for $0 < q < q_{01}$, where $q_{01} = \frac{2}{\pi} \left| \arctan \frac{|m| \sqrt{-\sigma_2\sigma_3}}{c_{12}} \right|$.

Hence, the assertion (i.2) holds. If $q = q_{01}$, then e_1^m is stable. For $q_1 < q < 1$, e_1^m is unstable $(\forall)m \in \mathbf{R}$.

(ii) Suppose $\sigma_2\sigma_3 > 0$. Then $\lambda_1 = c_{11}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm m\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}$.

(ii.1) Suppose $c_{11} < 0$ and $c_{12} < 0$. Then $\lambda_1 < 0$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm m\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}$. We have $\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 0$

and $\lambda_2\lambda_3 > 0$ if and only if $m \in \left(\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}}, -\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}} \right)$. In this case we have $\lambda_i < 0, i = \overline{1,3}$. Then the

eigenvalues are all negative for $m \in \left(\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}}, -\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}} \right)$. According to Corollary 3.1, and it follows that e_1^m

is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0,1)$. Also, e_1^m is unstable for $m \in \left(-\infty, \frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}} \right] \cup \left[-\frac{c_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}}, \infty \right)$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(ii.2) If $c_{11} < 0$ and $c_{12} > 0$, then $\lambda_1 < 0$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm m\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}$. We have $\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 2c_{12} > 0$.

Hence, $J(e_1^m, c_{11}, c_{12})$ has at least a positive eigenvalue and so e_1^m is unstable.

Therefore, the assertions **1(i)** and **1(ii)** hold.

Case 2. Let $c_{11} > 0$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$. Since $\lambda_1 = c_{11} > 0$, the Jacobian matrix $J(e_1^m, c_{11}, c_{12})$ has at least a positive eigenvalue and so e_1^m is unstable. Hence, the assertion **2** holds. \square

Corollary 4.1. Let be the fractional Stokes system (4.6) with the controls $c_{11}, c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$ and $m = 0$.

(i) If $c_{11} < 0$ and $c_{12} < 0$, then $e_0 = (0,0,0)$ is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0,1)$.

(ii) If $c_{11} > 0$ and $c_{12} \in \mathbf{R}^*$, then e_0 is unstable for all $q \in (0,1)$.

Proof. The characteristic polynomial of $J(e_0, c_{11}, c_{12})$ is $p_0(\lambda) = -(\lambda - c_{11})(\lambda - c_{12})^2$. The roots of the characteristic equation $p_0(\lambda) = 0$ are $\lambda_1 = c_{11}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12}$. Since $m = 0$, it implies $q_{01} = 0$. Now the statements (i) and (ii) of this corollary follow immediately from Theorem 4.1. \square

The eigenvalues of the controlled fractional system (4.6) for $m = 0$, before control are $\lambda_{1,2,3} = 0$ and after control are $\lambda_1 = c_{11}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{12}$.

Example 4.1. Let be the controlled fractional Stokes system (4.6) and $m = 0$. We select $l_1 = 0.92, l_2 = -0.05, l_3 = -0.15$.

(i) Choosing $c_{11} = -1.73, c_{12} = -2.05$ and according to Corollary 4.1(i) it follows that $e_0 = (0,0,0)$ is asymptotically stable $(\forall)q \in (0,1)$.

(ii) Choose $c_{11} = 0.35, c_{12} = -1.02$. By Corollary 4.1(ii), $e_0 = (0,0,0)$ is unstable for $q = 0.86$.

In Table 4.1 we give a set of values for $l_i, c_{11}, c_{12}, i = \overline{1,3}$ and the corresponding eigenvalues of controlled fractional system (4.6) for $m = 0$, before control and after control.

l_1, l_2, l_3	λ_i before control	Stability of e_0 $q \in (0,1)$	Controls c_{11}, c_{12}	λ_i after control	Stability of e_0 $q \in (0,1)$
$l_1 = 1.1, l_2 = 0.64$ $l_3 = -0.52$	$\lambda_{1,2,3} = 0$	unstable	$c_{11} = -1.08,$ $c_{12} = -0.24$	$\lambda_1 = -1.08,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = -0.24$	asym. stable
$l_1 = 1.1, l_2 = 0.64$ $l_3 = -0.52$	$\lambda_{1,2,3} = 0$	unstable	$c_{11} = -1.08,$ $c_{12} = 0.24$	$\lambda_1 = -1.08,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = 0.24$	unstable

Table 4.1. The controls c_{11}, c_{12} , equilibrium state e_0 and corresponding eigenvalues

The eigenvalues of the controlled fractional system (4.6) for $m \neq 0$, before control are:

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm i\sqrt{-\sigma_2\sigma_3}, \text{ if } \sigma_2\sigma_3 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}, \text{ if } \sigma_2\sigma_3 > 0.$$

and after control are:

$$\lambda_1 = c_{11}, \lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm im\sqrt{-\sigma_2\sigma_3}, \text{ if } \sigma_2\sigma_3 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = c_{11}, \lambda_{2,3} = c_{12} \pm m\sqrt{\sigma_2\sigma_3}, \text{ if } \sigma_2\sigma_3 > 0.$$

Example 4.2. Let be the controlled fractional Stokes system (4.6), $e_1^m = (m, 0, 0)$ for $m \neq 0$ and $q \in (0, 1)$.

(i) We select $l_1 = -0.42, l_2 = 0.2, l_3 = 0.6$. Then $\sigma_2 = 1.02, \sigma_3 = -0.64$ and $\sigma_2\sigma_3 = -0.652 < 0$.

Choosing $c_{11} = -0.6, c_{12} = 1.2$ and $m = 1.48$, we have $q_{01} = 0.5$. According to Theorem 4.1.(i.2) it follows that $e_1 = (1.48, 0, 0)$ is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0, 0.5)$ and unstable for all $q \in (0.5, 1)$.

(ii) We select $l_1 = -0.42, l_2 = 0.05, l_3 = -0.65$. Then $\sigma_2 = -0.23, \sigma_3 = -0.47$ and $\sigma_2\sigma_3 = 0.108 > 0$. Choosing $c_{11} = -1.2, c_{12} = -0.4$ we have $\lambda_1 = -1.2, \lambda_{2,3} = -0.4 \pm m\sqrt{0.108}$. According to Theorem 4.1.(ii.1) it follows that $e_1^m = (m, 0, 0)$ is asymptotically stable for all $m \in (-0.82, 0.82)$ and unstable for all $m \in (-\infty, -0.82] \cup [0.82, \infty)$. ($\forall q \in (0, 1)$).

(ii) Choose $c_{11} = 0.25, c_{12} = -2.2$. By Theorem 4.1.2, $e_1 = (0.8, 0, 0)$ is unstable for $q = 0.65$.

In Table 4.2 we give a set of values for $l_i, c_{11}, c_{12}, i = \overline{1, 3}$ and the corresponding eigenvalues of controlled fractional system (4.6) for $m \neq 0$, before control and after control.

l_1, l_2, l_3	λ_i before control	Stability of e_1^m $q \in (0,1)$	Controls c_{11}, c_{12}	λ_i after control	Stability of e_1^m $q \in (0,1)$
$l_1 = 0.8, l_2 = -0.2$ $l_3 = 0.2$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.774i$	$m = 1$ unstable	$c_{11} = -1.8,$ $c_{12} = -0.2$	$\lambda_1 = -1.08,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = -0.2 \pm 0.774i$	asym. stable
$l_1 = -0.42, l_2 = 0.2$ $l_3 = 0.6$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.807$	$m = 1.48$ unstable	$c_{11} = -0.6,$ $c_{12} = 1.2$	$\lambda_1 = -0.6,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = 1.2 \pm 1.19i$	$q_{01} = 0.5$ asym. stable $q \in (0, 0.5)$
$l_1 = 0.42, l_2 = 0.05$ $l_3 = -0.65$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.328$	$m = -0.4$ unstable	$c_{11} = -1.2,$ $c_{12} = -0.4$	$\lambda_1 = -1.2,$ $\lambda_2 = -0.2688,$ $\lambda_3 = -0.5312$	asym. stable
$l_1 = 1, l_2 = 1.6$ $l_3 = 0.4$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.6$	$m = 1$ unstable	$c_{11} = 0.25,$ $c_{12} = -1$	$\lambda_1 = 0.25,$ $\lambda_2 = -0.4,$ $\lambda_3 = -1.6$	unstable

Table 4.2. The controls c_{11}, c_{12} , equilibrium state $e_1^m = (m, 0, 0)$ and corresponding eigenvalues

• **Controllability of chaotic behaviors of the fractional Stokes system (3.4) around e_2^m**

Taking $d_1 = c_{21}$, $d_2 = c_{22}$, $d_3 = c_{21}$ and $u_e = e_2^m = (0, m, 0)$ in the fractional model (4.5) we obtain the following fractional system:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = \sigma_1 u^2(t) u^3(t) + c_{21} u^1(t) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = \sigma_2 u^3(t) u^1(t) + c_{22} (u^2(t) - m), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = \sigma_3 u^1(t) u^2(t) + c_{21} u^3(t) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0,1) \quad (4.7)$$

where $c_{21}, c_{22}, m \in \mathbf{R}^*$ are parameters.

The system (4.7) is called the *fractional Stokes system with the controls* $c_{21}, c_{22} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.

The Jacobian matrix of the fractional Stokes system (4.7) is

$$J(u, c_{21}, c_{22}) = \begin{pmatrix} c_{21} & \sigma_1 u^3 & \sigma_1 u^2 \\ \sigma_2 u^3 & c_{22} & \sigma_2 u^1 \\ \sigma_3 u^2 & \sigma_3 u^1 & c_{21} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Theorem 4.2. Let be the fractional Stokes system (4.7) with the controls $c_{21}, c_{22} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.

1. Let $c_{22} < 0$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$.

(i) Let $\sigma_1 \sigma_3 < 0$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(i.1) If $c_{21} < 0$, then $e_2^m = (0, m, 0)$ is asymptotically stable.

(i.2) If $c_{21} > 0$, then e_2^m is: asymptotically stable $(\forall) q \in (0, q_{02})$, stable for $q = q_{02}$ and unstable

$(\forall) q \in (q_{02}, 1)$, where $q_{02} = \frac{2}{\pi} \left| \arctan \frac{|m| \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_3}}{c_{21}} \right|$.

(ii) Let $\sigma_1 \sigma_3 > 0$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(ii.1) If $c_{21} < 0$, then e_2^m is asymptotically stable for all $m \in \left(\frac{c_{21}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}}, -\frac{c_{21}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}} \right) \setminus \{0\}$ and it is unstable

for all $m \in \left(-\infty, \frac{c_{21}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}} \right] \cup \left[-\frac{c_{21}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}}, \infty \right)$.

(ii.2) If $c_{21} > 0$, then e_2^m is unstable.

2. Let $c_{22} > 0$, $q \in (0,1)$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$. For all $c_{21} \in \mathbf{R}^*$, e_2^m is unstable.

Proof. Let be $p_2(\lambda)$ the characteristic polynomial of matrix $J(e_2^m, c_{21}, c_{22})$. The roots of the characteristic roots of $p_2(\lambda) = -(\lambda - c_{22})[(\lambda - c_{21})^2 - \sigma_1 \sigma_3 m^2]$ are $\lambda_1 = c_{22}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{21} \pm m \sqrt{|\sigma_1 \sigma_3|}$.

Applying the same reasoning as in the demonstration of Theorem 4.1 it is easy to prove that the the all assertions of this theorem hold. \square

The eigenvalues of the controlled fractional system (4.7), *before control* are:

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \quad \lambda_{2,3} = \pm i \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_3}, \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 \sigma_3 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \quad \lambda_{2,3} = \pm \sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}, \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 \sigma_3 > 0.$$

and *after control* are:

$$\lambda_1 = c_{22}, \quad \lambda_{2,3} = c_{21} \pm i m \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_3}, \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 \sigma_3 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = c_{22}, \quad \lambda_{2,3} = c_{21} \pm m \sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}, \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 \sigma_3 > 0.$$

Example 4.3. Let be the controlled fractional Stokes system (4.7), $e_2^m = (0, m, 0)$ for $m \neq 0$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(i) We select $l_1 = 0.6, l_2 = -0.1, l_3 = 0.8$. Then $\sigma_1 = -0.9, \sigma_3 = 0.7$ and $\sigma_1\sigma_3 = -0.63 < 0$.

Choosing $c_{21} = -1, c_{22} = -0.3$ and $m = 0.8$. According to Theorem 4.2.(i.1) it follows that $e_2 = (0, 0.8, 0)$ is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0, 1)$.

(ii) We select $l_1 = 0.72, l_2 = -0.6, l_3 = -1.09$. Then $\sigma_1 = 0.49, \sigma_3 = 1.32$ and $\sigma_1\sigma_3 = 0.6468 > 0$. Choosing $c_{21} = -1.2, c_{22} = -0.5$ we have $\lambda_1 = -0.5, \lambda_{2,3} = -1.2 \pm m\sqrt{0.6468}$. According to Theorem 4.2.(ii.1) it follows that $e_2^m = (0, m, 0)$ is asymptotically stable for all $m \in (-1.49, 1.49) \setminus \{0\}$ and unstable for all $m \in (-\infty, -1.49] \cup [1.49, \infty)$. ($\forall q \in (0, 1)$).

In Table 4.3 we give a set of values for $l_i, c_{21}, c_{22}, i = \overline{1, 3}$ and the corresponding eigenvalues of controlled fractional system (4.7) for $m \neq 0$, before control and after control.

l_1, l_2, l_3	λ_i before control	Stability of e_2^m $q \in (0, 1)$	Controls c_{21}, c_{22}	λ_i after control	Stability of e_2^m $q \in (0, 1)$
$l_1 = 0.6, l_2 = -0.1$ $l_3 = 0.8$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.793i$	$m = 0.8$ unstable	$c_{21} = -1,$ $c_{22} = -0.3$	$\lambda_1 = -0.3,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = -1 \pm$ $0.793i$	asym. stable
$l_1 = 0.72, l_2 = -0.6$ $l_3 = -1.09$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.804$	$m = 1$ unstable	$c_{21} = -1.2,$ $c_{22} = -0.5$	$\lambda_1 = -0.5,$ $\lambda_2 = -0.395,$ $\lambda_3 = -2.004$	asym. stable
$l_1 = 0.72, l_2 = -0.6$ $l_3 = -1.09$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.804$	$m = -1.6$ unstable	$c_{21} = -1.2,$ $c_{22} = -0.5$	$\lambda_1 = -0.5,$ $\lambda_2 = 0.086,$ $\lambda_3 = -2.486$	unstable

Table 4.3. The controls c_{21}, c_{22} , equilibrium state $e_2^m = (0, m, 0)$ and corresponding eigenvalues

• **Controllability of chaotic behaviors of the fractional Stokes system (3.4) around e_3^m**

Taking $d_1 = c_{31}, d_2 = c_{31}, d_3 = c_{33}$ and $u_e = e_3^m = (0, 0, m)$ in the fractional model (4.5) we obtain the following fractional system:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^q u^1(t) = \sigma_1 u^2(t) u^3(t) + c_{31} u^1(t) \\ D_t^q u^2(t) = \sigma_2 u^3(t) u^1(t) + c_{31} u^2(t), \\ D_t^q u^3(t) = \sigma_3 u^1(t) u^2(t) + c_{33} (u^3(t) - m) \end{cases} \quad q \in (0, 1) \quad (4.8)$$

where $c_{31}, c_{33}, m \in \mathbf{R}^*$ are parameters.

The system (4.8) is called the *fractional Stokes system with the controls* $c_{31}, c_{33} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.

The Jacobian matrix of the fractional Stokes system (4.8) is

$$J(u, c_{21}, c_{22}) = \begin{pmatrix} c_{31} & \sigma_1 u^3 & \sigma_1 u^2 \\ \sigma_2 u^3 & c_{31} & \sigma_2 u^1 \\ \sigma_3 u^2 & \sigma_3 u^1 & c_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Theorem 4.3. Let be the fractional Stokes system (4.8) with the controls $c_{31}, c_{33} \in \mathbf{R}^*$.

1. Let $c_{33} < 0$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$.

(i) Let $\sigma_1\sigma_2 < 0$ and $q \in (0, 1)$.

(i.1) If $c_{31} < 0$, then $e_3^m = (0,0,m)$ is asymptotically stable.

(i.2) If $c_{31} > 0$, then e_3^m is asymptotically stable $(\forall)q \in (0, q_{03})$, stable for $q = q_{03}$ and unstable

$(\forall)q \in (q_{03}, 1)$, where $q_{03} = \frac{2}{\pi} \left| \arctan \frac{|m| \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_2}}{c_{31}} \right|$.

(ii) Let $\sigma_1 \sigma_3 > 0$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(ii.1) If $c_{31} < 0$, then e_3^m is asymptotically stable for all $m \in \left(\frac{c_{31}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}}, -\frac{c_{31}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}} \right) \setminus \{0\}$ and it is unstable

for all $m \in \left(-\infty, \frac{c_{31}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}} \right] \cup \left[-\frac{c_{31}}{\sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}}, \infty \right)$.

(ii.2) If $c_{21} > 0$, then e_3^m is unstable.

2. Let $c_{33} > 0$, $q \in (0,1)$ and $m \in \mathbf{R}$. For all $c_{31} \in \mathbf{R}^*$, e_3^m is unstable.

Proof. Let be $p_3(\lambda)$ the characteristic polynomial of matrix $J(e_3^m, c_{31}, c_{33})$. The roots of the characteristic roots of $p_3(\lambda) = -(\lambda - c_{33})[(\lambda - c_{31})^2 - \sigma_1 \sigma_2 m^2]$ are $\lambda_1 = c_{33}$, $\lambda_{2,3} = c_{31} \pm m \sqrt{|\sigma_1 \sigma_2|}$.

To prove this theorem we proceed in the same way as in the proof of Theorem 4.1. \square

The eigenvalues of the controlled fractional system (4.8), before control are:

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm i \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_2}, \text{ if } \sigma_1 \sigma_2 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm \sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}, \text{ if } \sigma_1 \sigma_2 > 0.$$

and after control are:

$$\lambda_1 = c_{33}, \lambda_{2,3} = c_{31} \pm im \sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_2}, \text{ if } \sigma_1 \sigma_2 < 0;$$

$$\lambda_1 = c_{22}, \lambda_{2,3} = c_{21} \pm m \sqrt{\sigma_1 \sigma_3}, \text{ if } \sigma_1 \sigma_2 > 0.$$

Example 4.4. Let be the controlled fractional Stokes system (4.8), $e_3^m = (0,0,m)$ for $m \neq 0$ and $q \in (0,1)$.

(i) We select $l_1 = 0.6, l_2 = -0.1, l_3 = 0.8$. Then $\sigma_1 = -0.9, \sigma_2 = 0.2$ and $\sigma_1 \sigma_2 = -0.18 < 0$.

Choosing $c_{31} = -1, c_{33} = -0.31$ and $m = 0.48$. According to Theorem 4.3.(i.1) it follows that $e_3 = (0,0,0.48)$ is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0,1)$.

(ii) We select $l_1 = 0.9, l_2 = -0.18, l_3 = -0.36$. Then $\sigma_1 = 0.18, \sigma_2 = -1.26$, $\sigma_1 \sigma_2 = -0.2268 < 0$ and $\sqrt{-\sigma_1 \sigma_2} = 0.4762 < 0$.

Choosing $c_{31} = 1, c_{33} = -1.3$ and $m = 1.21$, we have $q_{03} = 0.33$. According to Theorem 4.3.(i.2) it follows that $e_3 = (0,0,1.21)$ is asymptotically stable for all $q \in (0, 0.33)$ and unstable for all $q \in (0.33, 1)$.

In Table 4.4 we give a set of values for $l_i, c_{31}, c_{33}, i = \overline{1,3}$ and the corresponding eigenvalues of controlled fractional system (4.7) for $m \neq 0$, before control and after control.

l_1, l_2, l_3	λ_i before control	Stability of e_3^m $q \in (0,1)$	Controls c_{31}, c_{33}	λ_i after control	Stability of e_3^m $q \in (0,1)$
$l_1 = 0.6, l_2 = -0.1$ $l_3 = 0.8$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.424i$	$m = 0.48$ unstable	$c_{31} = -1,$ $c_{33} = -0.31$	$\lambda_1 = -0.31,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = -1 \pm$ $0.424i$	asym. stable
$l_1 = 0.9, l_2 = -0.18$ $l_3 = -0.36$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.476$	$m = 1.21$ unstable	$c_{31} = 1,$ $c_{33} = -1.3$	$\lambda_1 = -1.3,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = 1 \pm$ $0.476i$	$q_{03} = 0.33$ asym. stable $q \in (0, 0.33)$
$l_1 = 0.9, l_2 = -0.18$ $l_3 = -0.36$	$\lambda_1 = 0$ $\lambda_{2,3} = \pm 0.476$	$m = 1.21$ unstable	$c_{31} = 1,$ $c_{33} = -1.3$	$\lambda_1 = -1.3,$ $\lambda_{2,3} = 1 \pm$ $0.476i$	$q_{03} = 0.33$ unstable $q \in (0.33, 1)$

Table 4.4. The controls c_{31}, c_{33} , equilibrium state $e_3^m = (0, 0, m)$ and corresponding eigenvalues

V. NUMERICAL INTEGRATION OF CONTROLLED FRACTIONAL SYSTEM (4.5)

Consider the fractional differential equations

$$\begin{cases} D^q u^i(t) = F_i(u^1(t), u^2(t), u^3(t)), & t \in (0, \tau), \quad i = \overline{1, 3}, \quad q \in (0, 1) \\ u(0) = (u^1(0), u^2(0), u^3(0)), \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} F_1(u(t)) = \sigma_1 u^2(t) u^3(t) + d_1 (u^1(t) - u_e^1) \\ F_2(u(t)) = \sigma_2 u^1(t) u^3(t) + d_2 (u^2(t) - u_e^2), \\ F_3(u(t)) = \sigma_3 u^1(t) u^2(t) + d_3 (u^3(t) - u_e^3) \end{cases} \quad d_1, d_2, d_3 \in \mathbf{R}^*.$$

Since the functions $F_i(t), i = \overline{1, 3}$ are continuous, then the initial value problem (5.1) is equivalent to non-linear Volterra integral equation of the second order ([5, 22]), which is given as follows:

$$\dot{u}^i(t) = u_0^i + \frac{1}{\Gamma(q)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} F_i(u^1(s), u^2(s), u^3(s)) ds, \quad i = \overline{1, 3}, \quad q > 0. \quad (5.2)$$

Diethelm et al. used the predictor-corrector scheme ([4]), based on the *Adams-Moulton algorithm* to integrate the equations (5.2).

We apply this scheme to fractional system (5.1). For this, let $h = \frac{\tau}{N}, t_n = nh$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

The controlled fractional Stokes system (5.1) can be integrated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} u^i[n+1] = u_0^i + \frac{h^q}{\Gamma(q+2)} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n a[j, n+1] F_i(u^1[j], u^2[j], u^3[j]) \right) + \\ \quad + F_i(u_p^1[n+1], u_p^2[n+1], u_p^3[n+1]), & i = \overline{1, 3}, \quad (5.3) \\ u_p^i[n+1] = \frac{h^q}{q\Gamma(q)} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n b[j, n+1] F_i(u^1[j], u^2[j], u^3[j]) \right) \end{cases}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} a[0, n+1] = n^{q+1} - (n-q)(n+1)^q \\ a[j, n+1] = (n-j+2)^{q+1} + (n-j)^{q+1} - 2(n-j+1)^{q+1}, & j = \overline{1, n}, \\ b[j, n+1] = (n-j+1)^q - (n-j)^q, & j = \overline{0, n}. \end{cases}$$

The above scheme given by the relations (5.3) is called the *Moulton-Adams algorithm for fractional system* (5.1), see ([4]).

The error estimate for the algorithm described by (5.3) is

$$\max_{0 \leq j \leq N} \left\{ |u^i[j] - u_p^i[j]| \mid i = \overline{1,3} \right\} = O(h^{q+1}).$$

Let us we apply the algorithm (5.3) and software Maple to integrate the controlled fractional Stokes system (5.1). For this, we take $h = 0.01, \varepsilon = 0.01, N = 500, t = 502$ and the initial conditions $u(0) = (u^1(0), u^2(0), u^3(0))$, where $u^i(0) = \varepsilon + u_e^i, i = \overline{1,3}$.

These considerations are exemplified in the following cases.

If in the relations (5.3) we replace the parameters d_i and the equilibrium states e_i^m for $i = \overline{1,3}$ with the values corresponding to the four situations of fractional model (4.5) studied, we will obtain the numerical integration of the fractional systems with controls (4.6), (4.7) and (4.8). More precisely, for:

– $d_1 = c_{11}, d_2 = c_{12}, d_3 = c_{12}$ and $u_e = e_0 = (0,0,0)$ we obtain the numerical integration (5.3).1

of the fractional model with controls (4.6) for $m = 0$;

– $d_1 = c_{11}, d_2 = c_{12}, d_3 = c_{12}$ and $u_e = e_1^m = (m,0,0)$ we obtain the numerical integration (5.3).2

of the fractional model with controls (4.6);

– $d_1 = c_{21}, d_2 = c_{22}, d_3 = c_{21}$ and $u_e = e_2^m = (0,m,0)$ we obtain the numerical integration (5.3).3

of the fractional model with controls (4.7);

– $d_1 = c_{31}, d_2 = c_{31}, d_3 = c_{33}$ and $u_e = e_3^m = (0,0,m)$ we obtain the numerical integration (5.3).4

of the fractional model with controls (4.8).

Example 5.1. Let us we present the numerical integration of the fractional Stokes system with controls (4.7) which has considered in Example 4.3(ii). For this we apply the algorithm (5.3).3. Then, in (5.3).3 we take: $l_1 = 0.72, l_2 = -0.6, l_3 = -1.09$,

$d_1 = -1.2, d_2 = -0.5, d_3 = -1.2$ and

$u_e = e_2 = (0,-1,0)$.

It is known that $e_2 = (0,-1,0)$ is asymptotically stable for $q = 0.92$. As an illustration of the application of algorithm (5.3).3 to integrate the system (4.7), we consider $h = 0.01, \varepsilon = 0.01, N = 100, t = 102$ and the initial conditions $u^1(0) = \varepsilon, u^2(0) = -1 + \varepsilon, u^3(0) = \varepsilon$. Using the package Maple we will obtain the graphical representation of the orbits $(n, u^1(n)), (n, u^2(n)), (n, u^3(n))$ and $(n, u^1(n), u^2(n), u^3(n))$ for $q = 0.7$ $q = 0.48$. of the discussed fractional model.

Remark 3.1. 3. Applying (5.3) and the package Maple for the numerical simulation of solutions of fractional models (4.6), (4.7) and (4.8) for each set of values for the parameters $l_i, d_i, i = \overline{1,3}$, given in the Tables 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4, it will be found that the results obtained are valid. The numerical simulations show the validity of the theoretical analysis.

Conclusions. This paper presents the fractional Stokes system (3.3) associated to dynamical system (2.5) in the case when $b = (0,0,0)$, denoted with (3.4). The fractional Stokes system (3.4) was studied from fractional differential equations theory point of view: asymptotic stability, determining of sufficient conditions on parameters $d_i, i = \overline{1,3}$ to control the chaos in the controlled fractional system associated to (3.4) and numerical integration of the controlled fractional model (5.1). The obtained results in the paper was illustrated with examples for their feasibility. The study of chaotic fractional systems has applications in theory of chaos synchronization and secure communications. In this context, by choosing the right control functions $\varphi_i(t), i = \overline{1,3}$ in the controlled fractional Stokes system (5.1), this work offers a series of chaotic and non-chaotic fractional differential systems.

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